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BENEFIT FOR WHOM? RESEARCHING THE TEACHING AND LEARNING ETHICS WITHIN ENGINEERING IN A DIVERSE CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

In teaching ethics within engineering, a key question is whether the learner is to be understood primarily as an individual or as part of a community. This tension is replicated in understanding the role of professional engineer where the engineer is both responsible for making autonomous decisions and for operating as part of a professional community.

Research about teaching ethics reflects a similar tension between research as an individual or collaborative activity. This raises questions about the ontology and epistemology of the researcher and the research subjects.

Learning theories address this tension in different ways, alternatively situating the learner as an individual or as part of a community. Engeström and Sannino's theory of expansive learning tackles issues of subjectivity, experience and identity in a way that usefully speaks to the challenges of researching the teaching and learning ethics within the professional space of engineering. They define learning as a *process*, where *process* is seen to be an inherently productive part of the teaching and learning relationship. Their emphasis on practice means their learning theory is inherently a research practice.

This analysis uses Sfard's distinction between language as a *tool* for communicating and as the *object of research*. Engaging critically with language around the teaching and learning of ethics as an object of research (using language as a shared tool) opens up the space to engage with policy and practice in a potentially transformative way. The paper concludes by summarising the value of practicing research as a way of engaging critically and constructively with the world.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Engeström and Sannino challenge us that the “ultimate test of learning theories is how they help practitioners to generate learning that grasps pressing issues that humankind is facing” [1]. This paper sets out to test the kind of research that might emanate from practitioners operating within the field of teaching ethics to engineers in terms three distinct learning theories. The research question thus is, “To what extent do the particular characteristics of a learning theory held by the researcher influence the kind of research that would be formulated in a specific context?”

The assumption would be that the researcher, consciously or unconsciously, selects a research strategy that relates to the epistemology encapsulated in the learning theory. Epistemology, as the theory of knowledge, relates intimately to the associated theory of learning.

Several recent SEFI special interest seminars relating to the teaching ethics within engineering have challenged participants to reconsider the way in which emotions were acknowledged and incorporated both in the teaching of ethics and in research relating to ethics within engineering. As an academic within the higher education sector in South Africa, this challenged me to consider the role of emotion in my own research.

South Africa can be positioned as a low to middle income-country with complex social challenges, including widespread youth unemployment and a perceived skills shortage. In this context, the strident political call for “radical economic transformation” has been seen to gather increasing public support in the face of wide-scale perception of public service ineptitude and corruption, polarising and simultaneously disempowering citizens where problems – and solutions – are positioned as structural rather than surmountable. Increasing cynicism and anger is accompanied by a revival of confrontation and the use of revolutionary language as a tool, or even weapon, to address service delivery failure.

In the context of these demands and challenges, questions emerge as to the use and value of research within higher education. As an academic in engineering education at a prestigious institution, I am forced to confront my own motives and vision in researching the teaching and learning of ethics relating to engineering: How do I use the tools of language to effect change? Does research engender real change? How can research contribute to transforming situations? Who benefits from the research?

This paper will examine *research* as a practice that investigates and makes visible phenomena that were previously “invisible” and that have potentially transformative effects beyond their direct environment.

This research emerged, in part, from a personal existential crisis as a result of an unexpectedly vehement emotional response to a piece of published research. The offending research appeared to be based on trivial and inconsequential data, artfully arranged and articulately argued, that gave a damning and inaccurate account of a

situation that I was emotionally invested in. At the same time, the article profiled valid and pertinent issues at the cost of my hard earned peace of mind.

The result of the emotional turmoil was a critical reflection on research in general, questioning what is possible in research, what I wanted to be a part of, what is considered useful and how to justify or anticipate the potential value of the research.

Three metaphors of learning will be examined that contribute different perspectives on what learning entails. A metaphor, by definition, requires the use of a concept outside of its usual sphere of reference. The metaphor intrinsically connects the way in which we perceive and process reality with how we translate knowledge of one entity to another. By keeping the attention on the metaphor rather than the theory, it prompts us to remember that the way we talk about “things” is more a tentative grasping towards meaning than a direct representation [2].

The three metaphors of learning will be connected to specific theories and linked to relevant research practices. Some of the theories of learning explicitly make these connections but, in others, the connections may be more implicit. These metaphors of learning are not seen as competing approaches but instead highlight complementary approaches to learning that in turn draw attention to, and validate, distinct research processes. Research thus is seen to be inextricably intertwined in the learning project and with the particular theory of learning that the researcher holds.

The challenge of researching the teaching and learning of ethics within engineering will be examined as an opportunity to explore how the way in which research is formulated potentially reflects the distinctive learning theory held by the researcher.

Sfard’s distinction between the use of language as a *tool* of communication and as an *object* of communication will be used to bring into focus the difficulty of reflecting on a problem using the very elements that are being questioned [3]. The consequence of this is that language is no longer the invisible net that holds a discipline together. It becomes instead the object of study: to be subject to examination, and its use negotiated within a context.

In this paper, the intention is to apply Sfard’s “model” or gaze to the practice of researching the teaching of ethics within engineering in South Africa. For Sfard, the “questions one finds worth studying depend on how the phenomena under study is conceptualized” [3]. The task thus becomes to scrutinize how the phenomena relating to the area of study – that of ‘teaching and learning ethics within engineering’ – are conceptualized.

The application of Sfard’s model can be justified in that, while her focus is the teaching of mathematics, similar imperatives operate within associated disciplines, engineering being one of these. Engineers are, in general, drawn from a cohort that has excelled in mathematics and science, where ability with language was not recognised to be central to the practice of the discipline. In this way, it may be seen that the experienced disruption to the engineering industry, as it shifts away from operating as a uniform cultural and linguistic entity to a multicultural and diverse

body, focuses attention on the way in which language may be considered both a tool and an object of research within engineering, specifically as regards researching the teaching and learning of ethics.

Alongside the investigation of the way in which research and epistemology are intimately related is a personal exploration of purpose relating to practicing research within a particular context.

2 LEARNING THEORIES CHARACTERISED AS METAPHORS

At its simplest, theory may be described as making inferences from facts. Facts can be described as having little value or meaning unless they are linked through inferences and the application of metaphor so as to represent a perspective on or of reality. Sfard defines a metaphor as very much a “conceptual transplant” and so the use of conceptual theories may be seen as inherently to involve transfer of meaning from one medium to another.

2.1 Learning as acquisition

The metaphor of learning as acquisition [3] may be seen to assume knowledge as objective and universal. This metaphor also suggests that learning might be measurable – be weighed or compared like a physical object. This understanding places the emphasis on the value and marketability of learning that can be transferred from a source to a person.

A theoretical approach that may be linked to the metaphor of learning as acquisition is that of positivism based on an understanding of the world as rational and objective, knowable through logic and deductive thinking. The emphasis on an rational world suggests that research intertwined with learning as acquisition will look to establish objective connections and comparative data about existing facts. Research will likely use experimental method and focus on quantitative method and measurable results. The assumption being that what can be measured, can be known.

An example of research to do with the teaching and learning of ethics, based in a conception of learning as transfer, would be to examine and to clarify the terms relating to ethics within a particular document so that the meaning of the words could be accessed and reproduced correctly.

2.2 Learning as participation

The metaphor of “learning as participation” [3] traces its roots to systems of apprenticeship where knowledge is passed on through the process of communities of practice.

Lave and Wenger’s [4] focus on communities of practice and the learning embedded within activity, context and culture is important for understanding the student’s “legitimate peripheral participation” in the professional space of the engineer and in the research process. While the focus of this peripheral participation may be seen to be the individual student’s learning, there is the associated contribution of peripheral

participants, that keeps the system running and generates real and potential benefits. As “peripheral participants”, the students’ gaze plays a potentially significant role constituting the shared practice.

Wenger [5] distinguished four components of learning as a social theory: that of *community* - of “learning as belonging”; that of *identity* - of “learning as being”, that of *meaning* - of “learning as experience” and that of *practice* - of “learning as doing”. In this Wenger’s attention is fixed more on developing the identity of the learners than on the “how” or “what” of the skills or knowledge that accompanies the process of taking on identity. Wenger sees learning as necessary, but not the direct result of inputs or the instructor, his theory speaks more to the learning that takes place informally rather than in the formal environment.

This metaphor of learning can be associated with research seen as participation in research projects (moving from the periphery to the centre), of learning to research within a team with the support of experts within the process. The focus is on finding identity as a researcher within the team, on the experience, the learning as doing, the belonging and the meaning in the experience of the research practice. Research can be seen to be a self-perpetuating process in which people find a role and a place. Wenger’s emphasis on the confidence that is developed within the social learning situation can be usefully translated into the research process which will be seen to build the confidence and assurance of the research practitioners. Research to do with teaching and learning ethics in engineering would be built on an understanding of learning taking place as a result of participation in communities of practice. This could include research on the reflective learning that takes place when a student is involved in a community of practice, such as that of work experience. Because of the understanding of shared meaning within a community, the methodology may involve the analysis of text or speech embodying the student’s articulation of their own learning. This could be incidental, as part of an assignment, or, more overtly, as part of an interview process. The research would focus on the learning relating to the developing sense of engineering identity in the student.

2.3 Learning as transformation

Engeström and Sannino [1] critique the sufficiency of the two previous metaphors in that they see that the associated models of learning assume learning to be something already existing, that can be received or passed on, but that do not account for the creation of new knowledge. They put forward a third metaphor, that of learning as transformation.

The theory of learning that this metaphor is seen to be built on is that of “expansive learning” that forms part of the wider theoretical approach of activity theory [6]. It identifies a triangulated concept of subject, object (context) and mediated artefact. Actions are seen to have a defined beginning and end, whereas activity is conceptualized as a continuous, collective interaction of the individual subject within their context that produces a learning artefact. The introduction of the concept of a learning artefact enables the analysis of the artefact independent of either the subject

or the object. This theory is intentionally creative, where learners co-create learning. Engeström and Sannino's [1] account of learning as transformation positions learning as requiring time and process, where this process is seen to be inherent in the teaching and learning relationship. They recognize the inter-related nature of teaching and learning, where the contribution of both instructors and learners is significant in the process of learning. They recognize the substantial role of instruction in the process of learning, but, in addition, identify a new space for learning to occur. This is articulated as a "gap between instruction and learning", where they identify "interesting things" to happen [1]. This opens the possibility of transformative learning beyond the intended consequences of the instruction. Engeström and Sannino's theory of expansive learning puts the attention on the collective activity of the learning community, where, together, learners learn "something that is not yet there" [1].

The most important outcome of expansive learning is seen to be *agency*: the participants' ability and will to shape their activity systems. This theory is developed further by Engeström and Sannino to tackle issues of subjectivity, experience, embodiment and identity [1] in a way that usefully speaks to the challenges of teaching and learning ethics within the professional space of engineering in complex social environments. This recognises the inter-related nature of learning and instruction, that they define as a dialectical relationship.

In research into the teaching and learning of ethics in an online context, this construct would allow the learner to be positioned as the subject, learning to be positioned as the object and the online learning management system, that contains both the instructor's intent and implementation, and the learner's engagement and response, to be positioned as the artefact.

The fact that learning is positioned as a process, angled towards transformation, gives additional impetus to connect Engeström's theory of expansive learning to its embodiment as a research practice. Here research by the participants – the ethics instructors or the learners themselves – on their own practice or context provides an example of research as transformation.

3. DISCUSSION

Engineering programmes recognize language as a *tool for communication*, where facility in communication is recognized as part of the requirements for practicing engineering. This is addressed in global accreditation programmes and, specifically, in the South African accreditation system, as graduate attribute 6, requiring proficiency in both verbal and written skills relating to technical and professional communication.

In addition, language can be approached as an *object of study* – critically engaging with the vocabulary and syntax that makes up the discourse of a discipline.

In this connection, *ethics* can be positioned as one of Meyer and Land's "threshold concepts" that operates as a "conceptual gateway to understanding" [7]. In this connection, the author's [8] analysis of the Engineering Council of South Africa's

accreditation process, identified a lack of clarity in the use of specific terms relating to ethics, where meaning was assumed to be clear. This assumption of clear communication was recognized as a problem preventing the development of a deep shared understanding of key concepts, thus inhibiting effective and sustained communication about ethics within the engineering space. Ethics was seen to be invisible because of an assumption that the meaning of concepts was inherent in the words used, where meaning is passed on through transference or through diffusion within a community. The assumption of shared meaning in the use of key terms to do with ethics fails to recognize that, when communities are dynamic and represent a diversity of members or practitioners, meaning may be tentative and transient, requiring collaborative action to build meaning within the context. In situations like this, communities need to actively grapple with the meaning of key concepts to ensure their relevance and use in the discourse of the community. Without explicit engagement, talk about ethics risks being relegated to a shallow level where it does not impact the day to day discourse of the community or feature prominently in the key areas of knowledge and skill within the discipline.

Research thus has a responsibility to engage critically and constructively with student formulations of their own learning relating to ethics and with educators' reflection on their practice of teaching relating to ethics.

This process of engaging critically and reflectively with an emotional response thus enabled me to use the energy constructively to interrogate and formulate more clearly what I was aiming to achieve through my research.

4 SUMMARY

Research is action. It is advocacy. It is a bringing to light of what is not yet visible and a shaping of a space for change to occur. It is presenting a lens to see through and then walking the reader (participant) through the process of looking. It is presenting an argument that allows the reader to see differently – to categorise differently – to act differently because of the new information. Because of the vision encapsulated in the research project. It turns the reader of research – no longer the passive consumer – into an active participant in the project of transformation – of shaping reality.

Research is thus a social activity. It takes place amongst a community, those you quote (and may or may not have met) and those who read what you have written. It involves and is affected by the research subjects (whom I am not convinced should be anonymous). It involves stakeholders (both those you involve in the research process and those you do not). To me, the research subjects have a substantiveness – an authority and a dignity – that could stand scrutiny. They are an integral part of the research process and need to be acknowledged and credited for their input. Published research thus needs to affirm the contributions of the research subjects as a group if not individually.

On a personal level, what I am thus trying to do with my research – and with my practice – is to make visible the potential energy and resources for change and

transformation that already exists in the research environment, and to open a space for the varied stakeholders to contribute to making things better and to be able to measure their own progress. To change the discourse from the focus on technical activities to the purposeful action of communities. To include and profile the value that collaborative action can produce. To make space for stakeholders to participate in a common task of transformation that involves them – and others – in a project that consciously or subconsciously translates the vision and aspiration of stakeholders – and research subjects – in such a way as to enable each stakeholder to be an active part of the change process.

There is the desire to model a process that others can follow - to see research participants engage as co-collaborators in a change project: where people's vision of what is possible – of what they can do, of what public institutions can do, opens up and is transformed in a collaborative and dynamic way.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y Engeström and A Sannino (2010), "Studies of expansive learning: Foundations, findings and future challenges" *Educational Research Review*, Vol. 5, pp. 1–24.
- [2] A Sfard (1998), "On Two Metaphors for Learning and the Dangers of Choosing Just One" *Educational Researcher*, Vol. 27, No. 2, pp. 4-13
- [3] A Sfard (2021), "Bewitched by language: Questions on language for mathematics education research", Chapter 3 in Planas, C. Morgan, & M. Schütte (Eds.), *Classroom research on mathematics and language*, London: Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9780429260889-4.
- [4] J Lave and E Wenger (1991), *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- [5] E Wenger (1998), *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning and identity*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, pp. 225.
- [6] Y Engeström (1999), "Expansive Visibilization of Work: An Activity-Theoretical Perspective," *Computer Supported Cooperative Work* 8, pp. 63–93.
- [7] J Meyer and R Land (2005), "Threshold Concepts and Troublesome Knowledge: Epistemological Considerations and a Conceptual Framework for Teaching and Learning." *Higher Education*, Vol. 49, No. 3, pp. 373–388.
- [8] A Gwynne-Evans, M Chetty and S Junaid (2021), Repositioning ethics at the heart of engineering graduate attributes, *Australasian Journal of Engineering Ethics*, Vol 26, No. 1, pp. 7-24.